

Evaluating the Efficacy of Customized Fertilizers in Sweet Potato Cultivation

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ABSTRACT

Sweet potato crop production is experiencing a decline in nutrient content due to intensive farming practices and imbalanced fertilization. Since crops obtain their minerals and nutrients from the soil, adequate soil nourishment is key to meeting this crop requirements and producing nutritious food for our daily consumption. Indian soils often lack essential nutrients, but customized fertilizers, both for soil application and foliar spray, developed using smart technology can bridge this gap by providing region-specific, soil-specific and crop-specific nutrient solutions. With this objective in mind, an experiment was conducted to develop a comprehensive package of practices tailored to sweet potato crop with 'Bhu Kanti' – a beta carotene rich variety.

The findings revealed that the treatment denoted as T2, involving soil application of customized fertilizer (650 kg ha⁻¹), applied twice—once as basal (325 kg ha⁻¹) and again after one month of planting (325 kg ha⁻¹)—combined with foliar application of Micronol Sweet Potato at a concentration of 5 ml lit⁻¹, administered three times on the 15th, 30th and 45th days after planting, yielded the higher number of tubers per plant (3.27), tuber yield per plant (404.03 g), marketable tuber yield (14.18 t ha⁻¹) and total tuber yield (17.70 t ha⁻¹) with highest net realization of Rs. 2,87,002.

Keywords: Bhu Kanti, Customized fertilizers, Economics, Micronol, Sweet potato.

INTRODUCTION

Nutrient deficiencies in soil are a growing concern, making customized fertilizers essential for balanced fertilization in sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas* (L.) Lam.) crops. Customized fertilizers, which are formulated based on a crop's specific nutrient requirements and soil conditions, offer a promising approach to achieving this balance (Kumar and Singh, 2015). The validation of these customized fertilizers is crucial, as it involves evaluating their effectiveness in promoting sweet potato growth, yield and quality under various conditions (Sekhon *et al.*, 2012). By conducting thorough field trials and assessments, researchers and farmers can determine the optimal fertilizer blends that meet the crop's nutritional needs, minimize environmental impact and maximize economic benefits (Vidyashree and Murali Arthanari, 2021). This is key to developing sustainable and efficient fertilization strategies for sweet potato cultivation, ultimately contributing to improved food security and agricultural productivity.

Crop productivity is intricately linked to soil fertilization and even minor adjustments in fertilization strategies can have profound impacts on overall yield (Das and Mitali, 2015). Sweet potato, being a nutrient-responsive crop, greatly benefits from optimized fertilizer application. However, the inefficient use of fertilizers by farmers, coupled with limited access to affordable credit, poses significant challenges to maximizing crop productivity (Darko *et al.*, 2020). To overcome these hurdles, improving fertilizer use efficiency is crucial for optimizing nutrient uptake and enhancing sweet potato tuber yield. While customized fertilizers have been shown to improve yields in various crops and soil types, there is a notable dearth of research on their specific impact on sweet potato (Vidyashree and Murali Arthanari, 2021). Furthermore, the potential benefits of micronutrients, such as Micronol, in sweet potato production remain underexplored. Indian Council of Agricultural Research - Central Tuber Crops Research Institute (ICAR-CTCRI) has developed a customized liquid micronutrient

formulation, commercially known as 'Micronol Sweet Potato', which contains essential micronutrients like zinc, copper, boron, iron and manganese *etc.* Given the importance of sweet potato in food security, it is essential to investigate the effects of customized fertilizers and Micronol on its performance (Susan John *et al.*, 2023).

Customized fertilizers are often developed based on soil test results to ensure optimal nutrient application. Sweet potatoes require a balanced mix of macronutrients (N, P, K) and micronutrients (e.g., B, Cu, Fe, Mn, Mo, Zn) for optimal growth (Anju *et al.*, 2018; Susan John *et al.*, 2005). Customized fertilizers can be tailored to meet the specific nutrient requirements of sweet potatoes, taking into account factors like soil type, climate and crop variety. Micronutrients play critical roles in various physiological processes, such as photosynthesis, enzyme function and stress tolerance (Ananda and Patil, 2005). Deficiencies in these micronutrients can significantly impact sweet potato yields and quality and customized fertilizers can help address these deficiencies (Kalra *et al.*, 2011).

Customized fertilizers can help optimize sweet potato yields by providing the necessary nutrients in the right proportions. By minimizing excess nutrient application, they also contribute to maintaining soil health and reducing environmental impact. Providing the necessary micronutrients, these fertilizers can help improve sweet potato quality, including their flavor, texture and nutritional content (Susan John *et al.*, 2023). Central Tuber Crops Research Institute (CTCRI)'s innovative, certified micronutrient liquid formulation promotes healthy plant growth, corrects deficiencies, enhances yield, quality and boosts resistance to diseases and stress in sweet potato crop (Susan John *et al.*, 2023). A customized micronutrient formulation for sweet potatoes, developed by Indian Council of Agricultural Research - Central Tuber Crops Research Institute (ICAR-CTCRI), contains zinc (2%), copper (0.6%), boron (0.2%), iron (0.5%), and manganese (0.25%). The recommended application is to

dilute 1 liter of the formulation in 200 liters of water for 1 acre (Susan John *et al.*, 2023). Micronol might be used as an additive to customized fertilizers to enhance their effectiveness or provide additional benefits, but further research is needed to determine its specific benefits and potential applications in sweet potato production.

This study aims to bridge the knowledge gap by evaluating the impact of customized fertilizers and Micronol on sweet potato yield and quality. By examining the interactions between these fertilizers and the crop's nutrient requirements, this research seeks to provide valuable insights for optimizing fertilization strategies in sweet potato production. The findings of this study will contribute to the development of more efficient and sustainable fertilization practices, ultimately enhancing crop productivity and food security.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experiment location

The experiment was conducted over two consecutive years (Y1: 2020-21 and Y2:2021-22) at the All India Coordinated Research Project (AICRP) on Tuber Crops Scheme, located at the Regional Horticultural Research Station, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari, Gujarat, India situated at approximately 20.95°N latitude and 72.93°E longitude. The sweet potato variety 'Bhu Kanti', known for its high beta-carotene content and yellowish-orange flesh, was used. The experimental site was prepared with deep tillage to aerate the soil and create a favourable seedbed. The plant spacing was 60 cm between rows and 20 cm between plants.

Treatment Details

The study evaluated the impact of a customized fertilizer and Micronol, a customized liquid micronutrient formulation, on sweet potato yield. Bhu Kanti, an improved variety of sweet potato which is popular in Gujarat was used in the treatment. This sweet potato variety was developed through clonal selection from an exotic line and is notable for its high β -carotene content, ranging from 6.2-7.8 mg/100 g.

Officially released in 2017 for cultivation in Odisha, and endorsed in Gujarat in the year 2018. This is recommended by Central Variety Release Committee - Central Sub-Committee on Crop Standards, Notification and Release of Varieties for Horticultural Crops in 2019 (No.3-72/2019-SD.IV). It yields an average of 20-24 t/ha of tubers. The variety exhibits a dry matter content of 24.0-26.6 %, starch content of 16.0-18.7 %, and total sugar content of 1.9-2.2 %. Developed by the ICAR-Central Tuber Crops Research Institute (CTCRI), Regional Centre, Bhubaneswar, this variety offers promising characteristics for sweet potato cultivation.

The experiment had three treatments:

T₁: Present Recommendation as per Package of Practices (POP): 75:50:75 NPK kg ha⁻¹ and 10 t ha⁻¹ Farm Yard Manure (FYM).

T₂: Fertilizer Best Management Practices (FBMP): Soil application of customized fertilizer twice (as basal and 1 Month After Planting - MAP) and foliar application of Micronol Sweet Potato at 5 ml lit⁻¹ three times (15, 30 and 45 days after planting).

T₃: Absolute Control: No FYM or fertilizers.

The composition of the fertilizers used was:

Customized Fertilizer: 11% nitrogen (N), 7% phosphorus (P), 11% potassium (K), 6% calcium (Ca), 3% magnesium (Mg), 0.4% zinc (Zn), and 0.1% boron (B).

Micronol Sweet Potato: 2% zinc (Zn), 0.6% copper (Cu), 0.2% boron (B), 0.5% iron (Fe), and 0.25% manganese (Mn).

Observations

Detailed observations were recorded to assess the impact of the treatments after harvest. Key parameters included according to 'Standard Operating Procedures for Tuber Crops' compiled by Sunitha *et al.*, 2020.

- Number of tubers per plant: The number of tubers per plant/vine is calculated by dividing the total number of tubers in net plot area by the total number of vines or plants in net plot area.
- Tuber yield per plant (g): Mean tuber weight per plant is worked out by dividing the fresh tuber weight in the net plot by the total number of plants.

- Marketable tuber yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$): Convert the weight of tubers after removing the damaged tubers recorded from the net plot to one hectare.
- Total tuber yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$): Convert the weight of tubers recorded from the net plot to one hectare.

These observations provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of the different treatments on sweet potato yield and productivity.

Statistical analysis

The experiment was conducted using a Completely Randomized Design (CRD), with

Table 1: Effect of fertilizer management practices on the number of tubers per plant and tuber yield per plant

Treatments	Number of tubers per plant			Tuber yield per plant (g)		
	Year 1 (Y1)	Year 2 (Y2)	Pooled	Year 1 (Y1)	Year 2 (Y2)	Pooled
T ₁	2.90	3.08	3.10	345.00	356.23	350.93
T ₂	3.10	3.30	3.27	398.40	409.80	404.03
T ₃	2.20	2.42	2.22	232.60	244.03	238.47
S.Em.±	0.09	0.08	0.08	11.58	11.74	10.10
C.D. _{0.05}	0.27	0.25	0.22	34.90	35.38	29.78
C.V. %	8.02	7.02	9.10	8.72	8.54	10.56
Y x T:						
	S.Em.±		0.11			14.28
	C.D. at 5 %		NS			NS

Table 2: Effect of fertilizer management practices on marketable and total tuber yield

Treatments	Marketable tuber yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$)			Total tuber yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$)		
	Year 1 (Y1)	Year 2 (Y2)	Pooled	Year 1 (Y1)	Year 2 (Y2)	Pooled
T ₁	12.73	14.26	13.33	14.56	16.54	15.67
T ₂	14.78	16.28	14.18	16.85	18.46	17.70
T ₃	10.01	11.52	11.18	11.51	13.09	12.35
S.Em.±	0.73	0.72	0.63	0.63	0.60	0.53
C.D. _{0.05}	2.19	2.17	1.85	1.89	1.80	1.57
C.V. %	14.21	12.59	16.82	10.74	9.14	12.06
Y x T:						
	S.Em.±		0.89			0.75
	C.D. at 5 %		NS			NS

RESULTS

The experiment's results showed significant differences in various yield parameters of the sweet potato crop, including the number of tubers per plant, tuber yield per plant, marketable tuber yield and total tuber yield, across the different treatments in each year of the experiment, as well as in the pooled analysis. The findings highlight the impact of the treatments on sweet potato production and yield characteristics.

Yield parameters

The results presented in Table 1 show the impact of different treatments on the number of tubers per sweet potato plant, with data for two years (Y1 and Y2) and a pooled average. Treatment T1 resulted

six samples per large plot, allowing for adequate replication and precise estimation of treatment effects. The data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) following the methodology outlined by Panse and Sukhatme (1967), a well-established statistical framework for analyzing horticultural experiments. This approach enabled robust conclusions to be drawn about the effects of the treatments on sweet potato yield.

in an average of 2.90 tubers per plant in the first year (Y1), which increased to 3.08 in the second year (Y2), with a pooled mean of 3.10 tubers per plant. In contrast, treatment T2 led to a higher number of tubers per plant, with 3.10 and 3.30 tubers per plant in Y1 and Y2, respectively. The pooled mean for T2 was 3.27 tubers per plant, indicating consistent and superior performance. Treatment T3 (the control) had the lowest number of tubers per plant, with 2.20 and 2.42 tubers per plant in Y1 and Y2, and a pooled mean of 2.22 tubers per plant. Overall, the results indicate that T2 outperformed the other treatments in terms of the number of tubers per plant, with a higher and more consistent yield across both years.

The highest tuber yield per plant was also achieved with treatment T2, with a pooled mean of 404.03 g, followed by T1 with 350.93 g, and T3 with 238.47 g. Statistical analysis revealed significant differences between the treatment means, with low standard errors and moderate variability. The treatment effects were consistent across both years, with no significant interaction between year and treatment.

The results in Table 2 show that treatment T2 resulted in the highest marketable tuber yield, with a pooled mean of 14.18 t ha⁻¹. This was followed by T1 with 13.33 t ha⁻¹ and T₃ with 11.18 t ha⁻¹. Statistical analysis confirmed significant differences between the treatment means, with T2 outperforming the others. The effects of the treatments were consistent over both years, showing no significant interaction between year and treatment.

The treatment T2 significantly outperformed and achieved the highest total tuber yield with a pooled mean of 17.70 t ha⁻¹ (Table 2). This was followed by T1 with a pooled mean of 15.67 t ha⁻¹, while the T3 control recorded the lowest yield at 12.35 t ha⁻¹. This consistency indicates that the relative performance of the treatments did not change significantly between years. Overall, the results demonstrate the effectiveness of treatment T2 in improving both marketable and total tuber yield, highlighting its potential as a valuable strategy for enhancing crop productivity. The success of customized fertilizers can be attributed to their tailored formulations, which ensure a balanced nutrient profile without introducing unnecessary or excess nutrients.

Table 3: Initial and final nutrient status of the soil for the first year

1 st Year	Initial nutrient status of the soil	Final nutrient status of the soil		
		T1	T2	T3
pH	8.42	7.66	7.8	8.1
Organic carbon (%)	0.66	0.72	0.84	0.65
Available N (kg ha ⁻¹)	228.93	200.03	215.87	150.19
Available P (kg ha ⁻¹)	24.75	27.34	29.83	23.27
Available K (kg ha ⁻¹)	463.68	465.56	467.72	464.52

Table 4: Initial and final nutrient status of the soil for the second year

Treatments	Initial					Final				
	N(kg/ha)	P(kg/ha)	K(kg/ha)	OC (%)	pH	N(kg/ha)	P(kg/ha)	K(kg/ha)	OC (%)	pH
	T1	200.03	27.34	465.56	0.72	7.66	185.4	29.8	468.6	0.74
T2	215.87	29.83	467.72	0.84	7.8	210.8	32.5	472.4	0.85	7.9
T3	150.19	23.27	464.52	0.65	8.1	101.2	22.5	460.5	0.64	8.08

Table 5: Economic analysis of sweet potato production

Treatment	Fixed cost	Variable cost	Total cost	Gross realization	Net Realization
T1	115790	15718	131508	399900	268392
T2	115790	22608	138398	425400	287002
T3	115790	1118	116908	335400	218492

Harvested tuber**Fig. 1:** Sweet potato experiment showcasing foliar spray and granular customized fertilizer application with harvested tuber

Treatment T₂, which included soil application of customized fertilizer twice (as basal and 1 month after planting - MAP) and foliar application of Micronol Sweet Potato three times (on 15, 30 and 45 days after planting), yielded superior results across all measured traits. In the pooled analysis, T₂ produced a higher number of tubers per plant (3.27), tuber yield per plant (404.03 g), marketable tuber yield (14.18 t ha⁻¹), and total tuber yield (17.70 t ha⁻¹) compared to the other treatments.

Soil nutrient attributes

The soil's initial nutrient status in the first year, was pH 8.42, 0.66 % organic carbon, and 228.93 N, 24.75 P and 463.68 K kg ha⁻¹. The soil analysis after treatment harvest of the second season 2021-22, the treatment T₂ showed improved nutrient status with pH 7.66, 0.72 %

organic carbon and balanced NPK levels (Table 3). In the second year, the treatments showed varying nutrient levels initially and finally. The soil properties before and after the experiment are as follows. Initially, the nitrogen (N) content ranged from 150.19 to 215.87 kg ha⁻¹, phosphorus (P) content from 23.27 to 29.83 kg ha⁻¹ and potassium (K) content from 464.52 to 467.72 kg ha⁻¹. The organic carbon (OC) content varied between 0.65 % and 0.84 % and the pH levels ranged from 7.66 to 8.1. After the experiment, the N content ranged from 101.2 to 210.8 kg ha⁻¹, P content from 22.5 to 32.5 kg ha⁻¹, and K content from 460.5 to 472.4 kg ha⁻¹. The OC content ranged from 0.64% to 0.85% and the pH levels were between 7.64 and 8.08. The treatment T₂ yielded the most favourable results, exhibiting the highest final values for nitrogen (210.8 kg ha⁻¹), phosphorus (32.5 kg ha⁻¹) and potassium (472.4 kg ha⁻¹) content.

Additionally, T2 recorded the highest final organic carbon content (0.85%). These outcomes suggest that T2 was the most effective treatment in enhancing soil nutrient levels and organic matter (Table 4).

Economic assessment parameters

Economic assessment parameters indicated that treatment T2 performed better over the other treatments. Treatment T2 was the most profitable treatment with a net realization of ₹2,87,002 due to its highest gross realization of ₹4,25,400, despite having higher variable costs (Table 5). The treatment T2, which involved soil application of customized fertilizer at a rate of 650 kg ha⁻¹, applied twice as basal and after 1 month of planting (MAP), combined with foliar application of Micronol Sweet Potato at a concentration of 5 ml lit⁻¹, sprayed three times on 15, 30 and 45 days after planting, resulted in the highest net realization of Rs. 2,87,002

DISCUSSION

Yield parameters:

The findings suggest that Treatment T2, involving two soil applications of customized fertilizer (at basal and 1 MAP) and three foliar sprays of Micronol Sweet Potato (on the 15th, 30th and 45th days after planting), yielded the best results among all the treatments. The customized fertilizer (CF) for sweet potatoes is a comprehensive solution that provides complete crop nutrition, including primary, secondary and micronutrients essential for optimal growth and development. Formulated based on sound scientific principles, integrated with soil information, laboratory studies and field research, CFs are designed to achieve a specific target yield. By delivering the right nutrients in the right proportions, CFs optimize nutrient uptake, improve crop performance and promote efficient use of resources, ultimately leading to enhanced yields and better crop outcomes in sweet potato. Whereas, 'Micronol Sweet Potato' is a foliar liquid micronutrient formulation specifically designed for sweet potatoes, comprising a balanced blend of 2% zinc (Zn), 0.6% copper (Cu), 0.2% boron (B), 0.5% iron (Fe) and 0.25% manganese (Mn). This precise

formulation is tailored to meet the unique nutritional requirements of sweet potatoes, providing a targeted boost to support optimal growth, development and productivity. Micronutrients in Micronol help sweet potato plants tolerate biotic and abiotic stresses, reducing yield losses and improving overall productivity.

According to Janssen *et al.* (1990), the principle suggests that when a specific nutrient is in short supply relative to others, the crop will meet its entire requirement for that nutrient from the soil alone. Customized fertilizers provide essential macronutrients (N, P, K) and micronutrients in the right proportions, ensuring that the crop receives a balanced nutrient supply that promote healthy tuber growth, allowing the plant to absorb more nutrients and water. Customized fertilizer application can improve soil fertility and structure, creating a more favorable environment for sweet potato growth. Potassium present in customized fertilizer influenced sweet potato tuber yield via an increase in the proportion of dry matter diverted to the tubers which rise in tuber number per plant.

Micronol, as a micronutrient supplement as a foliar spray, provides essential micronutrients that play critical roles in plant growth and development, such as enzyme function, photosynthesis and stress tolerance. Micronutrients like Mn, Fe, and Cu in Micronol play a crucial role in photosynthesis, leading to increased energy production and biomass accumulation. Micronutrients like Cu and Zn in Micronol have fungicidal properties, helping to protect the plant from diseases and reducing yield losses (Anju *et al.*, 2020 and Irfan *et al.*, 2017).

Foliar application of Micronol allows for efficient nutrient uptake, while soil application of customized fertilizer ensures a steady supply of nutrients to the tubers of sweet potato. The combination of customized fertilizer and Micronol promotes healthy plant growth, leading to increased tuber production and yield. According to Sharshar and Said (2000), this can be attributed to the increased availability of essential nutrients to the plants, as well as

improvements in the soil environment that promote better tuber growth in sweet potato, ultimately leading to enhanced water and nutrient uptake. Micronol and customized fertilizer application can address specific nutrient deficiencies, ensuring that the plant receives all the necessary nutrients for optimal growth (Kalra *et al.*, 2011). Similar trend for customized fertilizer also found by Elias *et al.*, 1991, Ali *et al.*, 2009, Agbede (2010), Byju *et al.*, 2016, Chen *et al.*, 2017, Anju *et al.*, 2020, Mandal *et al.*, 2020, Byju *et al.*, 2023 and Wenxue *et al.*, 2024 due to the addition of secondary and micronutrients in the required amounts, alongside primary nutrients, in the customized fertilizer formulation.

Soil nutrient attributes

According to Sung *et al.* (2016), customized fertilizers (CFs) differ from conventional chemical fertilizers in terms of the specific amounts of nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) applied, taking into account the unique chemical properties of the soil. In soil analysis, after the experiments, phosphorus, potash and organic carbon somewhat increased with the soil application of customized fertilizer two times as basal and after 1 MAP and Foliar application of 'Micronol Sweet Potato' @ 5 ml lit⁻¹ three times on 15, 30 and 45 days after planting. Customized fertilizer application likely provided a balanced phosphorus supply, promoting plant growth and tuber development. Phosphorus can also be retained in soil due to its adsorption onto soil particles. Potassium application through customized fertilizer can enhance soil potassium levels. Potassium is an essential nutrient for plant growth and its increased availability can benefit subsequent crops. The increase in organic carbon might be due to root biomass and exudates from sweet potato plants. Microbial activity stimulated by customized fertilizer and Micronol application, leading to increased decomposition of organic matter. The combination of customized fertilizer and Micronol application likely contributed to improved soil fertility and health, as reflected in the increased levels of phosphorus, potash and organic carbon. Results in line with Elias *et al.*,

1991, Sreelatha *et al.*, 1999, Agbede (2010), Chen *et al.*, 2017 and Wenxue *et al.*, 2024.

Economic assessment parameters

The efficacy of these treatments in enhancing crop productivity and profitability can be attributed to the synergistic effects of balanced nutrient supply and targeted micronutrient supplementation, ultimately leading to improved yields and economic returns. From an economic perspective, the resulting higher marketable yields and improved quality can translate to increased revenue for farmers. Furthermore, the optimized nutrient delivery can minimize waste and reduce the environmental impact of excess fertilizers in traditional method, thereby decreasing production costs. By leveraging these precision agronomic practices, farmers can improve their economic outcomes, increase their income and enhance the sustainability of their agronomic practices. The substantial net realization underscores the potential of this treatment as a viable and profitable strategy for sweet potato cultivation. Similar type of conclusion was found by Elias *et al.*, 1991 and Ali *et al.*, 2009.

CONCLUSION

The results of research revealed that out of three treatments, namely T1 followed the Package of Practices (POP) recommendation, applying 75:50:75 NPK kg ha⁻¹ and 10 t ha⁻¹ Farm Yard Manure (FYM). T2 employed Fertilizer Best Management Practices (FBMP), involving soil application of customized fertilizer twice and foliar application of Micronol Sweet Potato three times. T3 was the absolute control, receiving no FYM or fertilizers, the second treatment using customized fertilizers with Micronol Sweet Potato significantly boosted sweet potato yields and profits. Elaborately, the best results came from treatment T2, comprising customized fertilizers (650 kg ha⁻¹) twice [at planting (325 kg ha⁻¹) and one month later (325 kg ha⁻¹)] along with Micronol Sweet Potato foliar sprays (5 ml lit⁻¹) thrice on days 15, 30, and 45. This approach led to higher yields and better economic returns, likely due to the balanced nutrient supply that supported plant

growth. These findings suggest that the adoption of customized fertilizers and Micronol Sweet Potato can be a valuable strategy for sweet potato farmers seeking to enhance their crop productivity and economic returns, since these formulations provide a balanced mix of macro and micronutrients, meeting crop needs while preventing overuse of fertilizers.

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